

Unidentified species of *Longidorus* and *Xiphinema* were also occasionally found.

All three known nematode parasites of rice — *M. graminicola*, *H. oryzae*, and *T. martini* — probably cause significant yield reductions in deepwater rice in Bangladesh. *M. graminicola* root-knot nematode probably causes the most

damage to the aman crop. Typical field symptoms are yellowing and stunting, associated with the presence of *M. graminicola* females within roots and with some galling. *M. graminicola* can obviously tolerate flooding — large numbers of it were found in roots submerged in water as deep as 1.5 m, which was expected to reach more than

4-m depth later. The soil temperatures at the sites ranged from 31 to 36°C. The main *M. graminicola* damage appeared to be reduction in the ability of the deepwater rice plant to elongate so that it could not keep pace with the rising floodwater. In some situations, that could result in the complete drowning out of the crop. ■

Synergy between benomyl and carbofuran in the control of ufra

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) is a serious disease of deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. During 1978, an experiment on its chemical control when symptoms appear in the vegetative phase was laid out at a study site in Comilla District. A treated plot was arranged on each edge of a square untreated control plot to form a cross. All plots were 5 m x 5 m. The design reduced edge effects between treated plots as no two were contiguous along a boundary. Patchiness in disease distribution was also reduced as each treated plot was equidistant from the control and was surrounded by an untreated area. Four treatments were allocated randomly to the outer plots (see table). There were three replications in different fields. All were harvested in November.

Chemicals were applied in mid-August (soon after the appearance of chlorosis

Yield of rough rice at three sites with chemical treatment with carbofuran (F) and benomyl (B) after the appearance of symptoms of ufra attack in the vegetative phase.

Treatment ^a	Yield of rough rice (t/ha at 14% moisture)				
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Treatment totals	Treatment means ^b
F + B	1.54	1.53	1.86	4.93	1.64 ± 0.13 a
F + F	1.38	1.40	0.90	3.68	1.23 ± 0.13 ab
B + F	1.11	1.32	0.94	3.37	1.12 ± 0.13 bc
B + B	0.98	0.67	0.73	2.38	0.79 ± 0.13 cd
Control	0.45	0.96	0.61	2.02	0.67 ± 0.13 d
Block totals	5.46	5.88	5.04	16.38	1.09

^aThe first letter of each treatment represents application in mid-August; the second letter, application in early October.

^bAny two means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

and distortion of the young leaves) and just before panicle initiation in early October. Carbofuran, a granular insecticide, was applied to the floodwater (about 0.5 m deep) as Furadan 3G at 2 kg/m². Benomyl, a systemic fungicide, was applied to the foliage with a knapsack sprayer as Benlate 50 WP at 12.5 g/25 m². Since it is easier to detect synergy between two chemicals when the marginal physical product of one of them approaches zero, a high rate of carbofuran was necessary.

The analysis of variance indicates a significant difference between treatment effects (p<0.01). Two applications of benomyl did not give a significant yield

improvement. The three other treatment means were significantly different from the mean of the control plot (p<0.05). The significant difference between F + B and B + F may be explained either by the diminishing effect of carbofuran or an augmented effect of benomyl, as the time of application was postponed. There is evidence of a synergistic interaction between carbofuran and benomyl in the control of ufra. Although two applications of benomyl were less effective than two applications of carbofuran, carbofuran was less effective than benomyl after an initial carbofuran application. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Efficiency of granular herbicides and cultural methods in rice weed control

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Granular forms of 2 esters (isopropyl and ethyl of 2,4-D at 1.0 and 1.5 kg a.i./ha were compared for

efficiency in weed control with butachlor (G) at 2 kg/ha, nitrofen (G) at 2.0 kg/ha, propanil at 3.0 liters + 2,4-D Na salt at 0.8 kg a.i./ha, two hand weedings, a weed-free check, and an unweeded control in 1978 kharif. The weed flora in the experimental field included *Echinochloa colonum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus* spp., *Fimbristylis* spp.,

Ammania baccifera, *Ludwigia* spp., *Eclipta alba*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Potamogeton*, and *Anagallis arvensis*. The butachlor treatment had the lowest weed count, followed by 2,4-D EE at 1.5 kg/ha. The dry weight of weeds was lowest with 2,4-D IPE at 1.5 kg/ha — statistically the same level as that with 2,4-D IPE at 1.0, 2,4-D EE at 1.5 and

1.0, and nitrofen at 2.0 kg/ha. For early-maturing varieties such as Pusa 33-30, yields were highest with 2,4-D IPE at 1.0 kg/ha, followed by yield with nitrofen. These treatments were statistically similar to the weed-free check and two hand weedings. ■

Leaf scald disease of rice in Sierra Leone

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Although leaf scald disease of rice incited by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has long been present in West Africa, precise information about its economic significance is meager or entirely lacking.

From 1974 to the present the author has worked with the disease in farmers' fields and experimental plots. The following are general conclusions:

1. The disease is most severe in the uplands. Yield reductions from 9 to 12% were estimated from preliminary studies.
2. Severe infection (more than 25% leaf area desiccation) can occur in wet season paddy or irrigated rice. The disease appears insignificant on dry season crops.
3. Visible infection usually appears after the end of tillering. However, the disease has also been found in seedling nurseries.
4. Narrow-leaf varieties like ROK 3, PN 623-3, ADNY 8, and ROK 8 are less affected than broad-leaf varieties like

IRAT 8, Moroberekan, LAC 23, and ROK 16.

5. Broadleaf varieties that retain water droplets on the leaf surface are more susceptible to the disease.

6. The disease is more severe on fertilized than unfertilized plots. This susceptibility under varying soil fertility levels was particularly striking in Sierra Leone's "On Farm Trials" network where upland plots received 60 kg N/ha, 40 kg P/ha, and 40 kg K/ha.

At the Rokupr Rice Research Station, studies on yield loss, epidemiology, plant canopy characteristics, spacing, and fertility levels in relation to disease severity, are in progress. Additionally, varietal screening for total performance including resistance to scald is continuing. ■

Rice diseases during kharif in Karnataka, India

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Rice blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* occurs every year in the main rice-growing areas of Karnataka state. Neck blast is usually more damaging than leaf blast. Out of 683 NSN entries screened for blast, only 35 were resistant at Ponnampet during 1978 kharif:

IET6586, IET6731, IET6814, IET6868, IET6873, IET6876, IET6877, IET6880, IET6881, IET6882, IET6883, IET6884, IET6894, IET6899, IET6900, IET6907, IET6914, IET6916, IET6950, IET6951, IET6952, IET4554, IET5905, IET5909, IET5910, IET5911, IET6046, IET6260, IET4699, IET5735, IET6312, IET6663, IET6665, IET6667, and IET6669.

Brown leaf spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*), the next most important disease, occurs throughout the state.

Udbatta disease (*Ephelis oryzae*) has increased in recent years. Severe infection of high yielding dwarf varieties caused considerable yield loss.

The problems of grain discoloration increased after the introduction of high yielding varieties. The discolored grains are associated with organisms like *P. oryzae*, *Trichoconis oryzae*, and *Dreschlera oryzae*.

Leaf scald due to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has been observed in the past 7 to 8 years on high yielding varieties.

Other erratic and minor diseases like bacterial leaf blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*), false-smut (*Ustilaginoidea virens*), sheath blight (*Corticium sasakii*), and sheath rot (*Acrocyndrium oryzae*) have also been observed. ■

Acquisition of rice tungro virus through parafilm membrane by *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)

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The ability of 547 adult *Nephotettix virescens* to acquire the tungro virus from diseased leaves covered with parafilm was tested. After an acquisition access time of 1 to 4 days, 56 to 75% of the insects became infective on TNI seedlings (see table). In general, the percentage of infective insects increases as the

Percentage of infective *N. virescens* after acquisition feeding on tungro-diseased leaves covered with parafilm. IIRRI, 1979.

Acquisition access time (days)	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)
1	221	56
2	197	75
3	89	74
4	40	68

acquisition access time lengthens from 1 to 4 days. But in this test it decreased on the third and fourth day because the diseased leaves became necrotic from continuous insect feeding, and started to decay. The parafilm membrane did not hinder acquisition feeding by the insect. The method may therefore be used for developing a bioassay of the virus. ■

Field efficacy of stable bleaching powder to control bacterial blight of rice

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In a field trial during 1977 and 1978 kharif, stable bleaching powder (SBP) was tested for the control of bacterial blight of rice. Seedlings of Jaya were inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson by the clipping method 3 weeks after transplanting. Three 15 kg/ha applications of SBP were spread on fields having 4.5 to 5.0 cm of standing water to provide 10 ppm chlorine. The first application was made 72 hours before inoculation and subsequent applications were at fortnightly intervals. Disease incidence was recorded 2 weeks after the last application; the other observations were